

ARBITRABILITY AND JURISDICTION: REIMAGINING UZBEKISTAN'S LEGAL PROVISIONS (THESIS)

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Uzbek Law “On Insolvency” suggests that when there is a conflict of law in application of the insolvency laws between the domestic laws and international treaties, then the provisions of the international treaty shall apply, which is general rule reflected in other legislative norms as well as the Law on International Treaties of Uzbekistan¹ (LRU-518,06.02.2019). Although the article 6 of the law on Insolvency states that: “The insolvency case shall be considered by the court and the insolvency case in accordance with this Law shall be considered by the court on the basis of an application of a person entitled to apply to the court at the place of state registration of the debtor which is a legal entity, as well as at the place of residence of a natural person and (or) an individual entrepreneur”, this, in most cases, does not amount to bar arbitral competence to decline its jurisdiction in insolvency disputes, especially, when there is a “foreign element”.² English Law takes different approach through Insolvency Act. In case of personal bankruptcy, the Insolvency Act 1986 in Section 349A determines that the trustee can decide if the arbitration agreement is enforceable and if the trustee thinks it is not, a party can apply to court to have the arbitration agreement enforced. The trustee can also, with the permission of the court, make an agreement to arbitrate after bankruptcy is declared. If the arbitration is pending and bankruptcy is adjudged before arbitration terminates, the court can stay the proceeding but this is not a mandatory action, as the language used in the Act is “may stay any action.”³

As it has been reviewed by the previous sub-chapter, overall picture shows that the laws of Uzbekistan on Arbitrability takes general approach regarding arbitrability, reflecting the general provisions from international treaties. However, the law “On investment and investment activities”, sets requirements before the initiation of arbitration, particularly requiring to resolve the dispute through negotiation, mediation and state courts, and then if it is provided by the valid agreements, the investor can refer the dispute to the arbitration. But this does not necessarily mean that it apply in most cases, especially since the parties (including investor) has their autonomy, investors often avoid the choice of law of Uzbekistan as an applicable law. As investment contract is considered to an outcome of the negotiations between the investor and the government of Uzbekistan, as provided in the regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers “On the procedure for concluding, amending, terminating and implementing investment contracts between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a foreign investor”, and “Most foreign investment contracts are negotiated behind closed doors, and are not accessible to members of the public even after they are signed”⁴ and

¹ Available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/4830084>

² Article 1158 of the Civil code of Republic of Uzbekistan, Available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/180552>

³ The English Law Approach To Arbitrability Of Disputes, Leonardo V. P. de Oliveira, Available at: https://arro.anglia.ac.uk/id/eprint/701213/6/de%20Oliveira_2016.pdf

⁴ Strengthening Citizens’ Oversight of Foreign Investment: Investment Law and Sustainable Development, Sustainable Markets Investment Briefings, Briefing 4: Foreign investment contracts Lorenzo Cotula,

therefore, the other terms can be made in the contract in negotiations. However, practitioners state that this limitation under Uzbek investment law should be removed, because it leads to limitation of the access to arbitration. Foreign investors seek to resolve disputes at the international level relying on the principle of diplomatic protection. As a counterbalance to this, Uzbek law limits resort to arbitration by its national law. Regardless of that, investors do have a gateway to international forum in a number of ways. Direct access to arbitration would be granted to the foreign investor if the state gives written consent to arbitrate through arbitration agreement, which relies on MIT or BIT. Above that, investor may also have a direct recourse solely under BIT, save its ISDS provisions provide for the different order. In other scenarios, investor has to go through mandatory stage with domestic courts first and only after that file the claim against state on the international fora.⁵ However, “fork-in-the-road” provisions are common in international investment law practice and the approach of Uzbek law is not surprising, rather than arbitration, which over costed in previous disputes for the government, instead it is suggested that other laws regulating the initial steps of initiation of arbitration should also be in compliance with these provisions.

By precisely stating that in Law on International commercial arbitration and other relevant laws, the blurred line between the jurisdiction of domestic courts and arbitration could be clarified.

Real estate disputes, or the disputes related to “Landlord – tenant” are considered non-arbitrable in most cases, some countries take democratic approach in favor of the arbitrations. In India It started with the case of *Booz-Allen & Hamilton Inc v. SBI Home Finance Ltd & Others* (“Booz-Allen”), wherein the Supreme Court, after hearing the matter, held that the disputes relating to eviction and tenancy were not arbitrable. The court discussed that: under Section 8 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act (“Act”) wherein *“even if there is an arbitration agreement between the parties, and even if the dispute is covered by the arbitration agreement, the court where the civil suit is pending, will refuse an application under Section 8 of the Act, to refer the parties to arbitration, if the subject matter of the suit is capable of adjudication only by a public forum or the relief claimed can only be granted by a special court or Tribunal”*. Additionally, the practice of UAE, also indicate that there are public policy consideration while arbitrating real estate disputes. In one case in Dubai, The plaintiff further appealed the Dubai Court of Appeal’s decision before the Court of Cassation under Appeal No. 141 of 2022. On 29 November 2022, the Dubai Court of Cassation accepted the Appeal and overruled the Court of Appeal’s decision on the following grounds:–

- the developer’s procedures to unilaterally terminate a sale and purchase agreement before the Dubai Land Department as regulated under Article 1 of Law No. 19 of 2020 – which amends Article 11 of Law No. 13 of 2008 Interim Real Property Register in the Emirate of Dubai (mandatory rule) – are related to public policy;

International Institute for Environment and Development, Available at: <https://www.ied.org/sites/default/files/pdfs/migrate/17015IIED.pdf>

⁵ Malika Khushmatova, **Access to International Arbitration in investor-state dispute settlement (ISDS) in Uzbekistan**, Grata International, Available at: <https://gratanet.com/publications/access-to-international-arbitration-uzbekistan> .

- paragraph 2 of Article 4 of the UAE Arbitration Law No. 6 of 2018 stipulates that arbitration is not permissible in matters that do not permit compromise. Therefore, any dispositions of off-plan real estate properties cannot be a subject matter of arbitration.
- in the event that contracting parties agreed to resort their disputes to arbitration and the subject of the dispute relates to matters that cannot be conciliated, the competence to adjudicate over such disputes falls within the local courts' jurisdiction. Accordingly, it is not permitted for an arbitrator to determine a matter that relates to public policy, otherwise any award issued in this relation will be subject to nullification.⁶

It would be fair to determine that all disputes arising out of real estate are non-arbitrable, which also would be in compliance with the existing international practice, as well as the general meaning of the national laws, which often indicate land and other resources as national property and define real estate as "property connected with land". On the arbitrability issues of real estate, Prof. Sokhiba Inoyatova suggests that "It is advisable to provide for the implementation of state registration of transactions related to real estate and rights not to it, on the basis of an arbitration award in the presence of a mutual statement of the parties to the arbitration agreement and amendments and additions to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the procedure for state registration of rights to real estate" dated 29.12.2018 №1060. As you know, although disputes related to insolvency are not arbitrable, it is advisable at the legislative level to give creditors the right to apply for debt collection to international commercial arbitration before certain bankruptcy procedures, for example, before external management.⁷

In case if the disputes, which are discussed above cannot be expressly indicated or listed under Uzbek the law, at least the courts should be granted more authority to protect the public policy. Following the practice of the Eastern countries, China, Japan, and it is also reflected in the laws of the US that the domestic courts have enough authority to make determinations of the arbitrability issues.

28 Article¹. (4) of Economic Procedural code of Republic of Uzbekistan, indicates that: the cases on making decisions on the issue of jurisdiction of the arbitration court; however, it does not precisely indicate or list the actions that may be taken by the courts to determine the arbitrability, or whether this provision apply to the determination of if the subject matter of the dispute is arbitrable is under question. Therefore ,precise provisions of arbitrability in Law on international commercial arbitration would be effective for determinations of the courts and arbitral tribunals, as well as the participants of the arbitral process.

Article 30 of the EPC provides which disputes are reviewed by the courts , however, as insolvency disputes, the arbitrability of these disputes are not expressly mentioned.

In regulation of IP disputes, Article 1030 of the Civil Code provides that: Legal protection of intellectual property objects occurs as a result of their creation or as a result of being granted legal protection by an authorized state body in the cases and procedures provided for in this Code or other laws. Other Laws covering different spheres of intellectual property.

⁶ Public Policy and Arbitrability of Real Estate Disputes in the UAE, Mahmood Hussain Law Firm, Available at: <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=796b8943-218e-47aa-a4ca-2f3bc7234578>

⁷ Inoyatova Sokhiba Fazilovna, Arbitrability Of Disputes Under The Legislation Of Uzbekistan, Published Date: November 30, 2022 | Crossref doi: <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajpslc/Volume04Issue11-10>

However, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on “The establishment of the Tashkent International Arbitration Center (TIAC) under the chamber of commerce and industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 05.11.2018 No. PQ-4001, puts forward some functions to be performed ,section 1(a) provides that organization of settlement of disputes arising from contractual and other civil legal relations between commercial organizations located in different countries, including foreign investors, in particular, disputes related to investments, intellectual property and blockchain technologies through international arbitration. This indicates that there is a possibility of the change in the near future in favor of the arbitrability of IP disputes. Additionally, since Uzbekistan is a party to many treaties of the WIPO , applying to WIPO mediation and arbitration center is not restricted, but rather suggested by this organization.

To conclude, the line between arbitrability and non-arbitrability is often set through cases sources in Anglo-American legal systems, and interpretation of cases follow each other. For avoidance of confusion between these matters, it is advisable for the continental law family to expressly indicate limitations. Although Indian precedents interpreted the cases by listing the non-arbitrable subject matter of the disputes, I would consider that this would also be limitation on the independence or the competence of the arbitral tribunals. Therefore, the issues of arbitrability requires careful consideration, if it favors the public policy, it may interfere the competence of the arbitral tribunals, otherwise, the public policy and right to regulate. This could be done through Chinese approach, especially, by regulating organizational and jurisdictional disputes under exclusive court jurisdiction and then allowance of the arbitral process without court intervention.

In the past, arbitration was not seen as a legitimate alternative to litigation and was often prohibited. However, this has changed over the past few decades. In most countries in Europe and the United States, there are now few restrictions on arbitrability. African countries still have some restrictions, but they are becoming more open to arbitration. There are a number of subject matters that are particularly well-suited for arbitration, including intellectual property, antitrust, insolvency, family matters, labor law, and consumer protection. In the United States and South Africa, there were once restrictions on arbitration of disputes involving public policy or public interests, such as antitrust. However, these restrictions were lifted as legislators and courts gained confidence in the arbitral process. The trend towards expanding the scope of arbitrability is a welcome development. In the conclusion, I will discuss the arbitrability of disputes involving public authority, family disputes, and consumer and employment disputes. These are areas where arbitrability still needs further development.

The difference between arbitrability and exclusive competence is established on the basis of studying, as a rule, procedural laws and consists in resolving the issue of the purpose of the analyzed legal norms. If these rules imply a ban on the arbitration of cross-border commercial disputes, they are provisions on arbitrability (or, to be more precise, non-arbitrability). If these rules delimit the competence of the courts within the state -they are not included in the content of arbitrability. An important role in the interpretation of these norms is played by the establishment of their addressees (whether international commercial arbitration is included in the number of such addressees).

Courts have *de facto* a considerable discretion in applying the relevant statutes and their mandatory provisions. The guiding principle for the area of commercial representation, like any other areas of law where mandatory provisions play an important role, has been well summarized by the U.S. Supreme Court in *Mitsubishi v. Soler*. There the court stated: “By agreeing to arbitrate a statutory claim, a party does not forgo the substantive rights afforded by the statute; it only submits to their resolution in an arbitral, rather than judicial, forum. It trades the procedures and opportunities for review of the courtroom for the simplicity, informality, and expedition of arbitration.”

Arbitration must adhere to public policy and uphold fundamental principles of justice. Public policy concerns encompass various areas such as criminal law, antitrust regulations, human rights, labor rights, and consumer protection. Courts have a crucial role in determining whether a specific dispute goes against public policy and is therefore not suitable for arbitration. The notion of public policy is frequently invoked, as stated in Article V(2)(b) of the New York Convention, which allows for the refusal of recognition and enforcement of an award if it contradicts public policy. Additionally, many national arbitration acts include provisions related to public policy. However, there is no independent definition of public policy. Authors, arbitrators, and judges often refer to an internationally recognized standard when discussing public policy.

As discussed above this thesis puts forward some suggestions to improve the laws of Uzbekistan in the area of arbitrability. It is also crucial to mention that in determining arbitrability in laws, the drafts should be aware of the tendencies in the state policy, and the interpretation of the term “public policy” under national law and international treaties. First of all, it is important to clearly define the concept of arbitration in the legislation. Considering all these, from my perspective the following would increase efficiency in arbitral processes:

Firstly, since the state policy always supports the entrepreneurship and the business activities, arbitrability of the bankruptcy proceedings should expressly be determined. Although the “Law on Insolvency” state that courts have jurisdiction, this does not prevents the disputes to be reviewed by arbitration, especially if one party is a foreign national.

Secondly, resolving intellectual property disputes through arbitration is not restricted, under the current legislation, and since Uzbekistan is party to World Intellectual Property Organization, its treaties and other instruments, the question of arbitrability of these disputes could be positive. However, since there is a possibility of conflict of laws, the registration of the IP objects and patents should be considered carefully. Disputes concerning the safeguarding of intellectual property and intangible assets encompass various categories such as copyright protection, related rights, trademarks, trade names, useful inventions, industrial designs, models, business reputation, honor, and dignity, among others. These disputes can be resolved through arbitration, as long as there is an agreement to arbitrate them. However, according to legal literature, disputes that pertain to the status of registered intellectual property objects, such as debates regarding the protectability of an invention or the legality of registration or refusal of registration, are not suitable for arbitration. This is because the main opposing party in such disputes is typically a government agency, whose actions and decisions are being contested. This holds true even if the applicant or plaintiff is not the copyright holder, but a third party.

In third place, It is recommended to include provisions for the implementation of state registration of transactions involving real estate and associated rights, based on an arbitration award. This can be done when both parties involved in the arbitration agreement mutually agree and comply with the amendments and additions stated in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan titled "Measures to enhance the procedure for state registration of real estate rights," issued on 29.12.2018 with the number 1060. It is worth noting that disputes related to insolvency are typically not eligible for arbitration. However, it would be beneficial to grant creditors the ability, through legislative means, to seek debt collection through international commercial arbitration before certain bankruptcy procedures, such as external management, take place. Such legislative improvements would enhance the appeal of Uzbekistan's applicable laws and provide valuable support to the institution of international commercial arbitration.

One should also consider that narrowness of this definition of arbitrability has important consequences. In the first place, under this definition, the arbitrability or non-arbitrability of a claim or dispute should be readily ascertainable. It should not depend on the factual circumstances surrounding the claim. Used in this way, arbitrability entails a purely legal inquiry. Thus, however else one may understand the principle of arbitrator competence-competence, that principle would not prevent a court, if properly asked to do so, from declaring prior to arbitration that a claim or dispute is not arbitrable and should not be referred to arbitration.

Although setting a universal rule on the kind of disputes that can be settled by arbitration and therefore arbitrable, may be challenging, and one can agree that more international consensus on arbitrability among national laws would be desirable and would promote legal certainty.